

Wat Preah Vihear Sour: A Popular Pilgrimage Site outside Phnom Penh, Cambodia

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Wat Preah Vihear Sour is a pre-colonial Theravada Buddhist temple which was built before the 1860s on an older construction site belonged to the Angkor era (9th-15th centuries CE). The site has several constructions like a water reservoir (baray) which belonged to the Angkor period (9th-15th centuries). Theravada Buddhist practices/beliefs probably came to the area during the 16th century which has remained the most important element of the site until today.

Date Range: 1000 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Vihear Sour commune, Khsach Kandal district, Kandal province

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Cambodia

A post-Angkor Theravada Buddhist site, which served as Khmer Royal Capital between 15th-17th centuries CE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: The Nupbarat Khmer Palace chronicle of 1878, (EFEO's cat. no. P. Camb. 48), pp. 26-30

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

– Source 1: Commission des mœurs et coutumes du Cambodge: Prajuṃ Rīoēñ Preñ Khmer (Bhāḡ Praṃ) [Collection of Khmer folklores (Vol. 5)]. Phnom Penh: Buddhist Institute, pp. 37-43.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.khmertimeskh.com/60809/vihear-sour-tradition-set-to-continue/>

- Source 1 Description: While the advent of Pchum Ben afforded Cambodia’s sporting scene a much needed breather, thousands of Cambodians converged on Vihear Sour Cheung village, Kandal province – some 35 kilometers from Phnom Penh – for the annual games which traditionally mark the end of Pchum Ben festivities
- Source 2 URL: http://dept.sophia.ac.jp/is/angkor/publication/pdf/bunka/bunka29_03.pdf
- Source 2 Description: Vihear Suor is a site that was considered as being located in the region of Srei Santhor of the Kompong Cham province, but it now belongs to the Kandal province. In the middle period, the area was considered as a connecting gate between Srei Santhor and other areas such as Phnom Penh, Thong Khmum (Ba Phnom), and Prei Nokor (Saigon)
- Source 3 URL: <https://english.cambodiadaily.com/news/pagoda-gets-holiday-started-with-buffalo-races-49998/>
- Source 3 Description: vihear sour commune, Khsach Kandal district, Kandal province – With businesses and government offices around the country closed for the three-day Pchum Ben celebrations, thousands of people began flocking on Sunday to Preah Chas village to take part in one of the festival’s most celebrated events

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

A single structure

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Specify

– Private individual

– Other [specify]: senior members of Cambodian government

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Specify

– Revealed by semi-divine human(s)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Specify

– Birthplace of divine or semi-divine human(s)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 50

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 25

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: sand stone and brick

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: cement and wood

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: statues of the Buddha, deities, Khmer heroes

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Depiction of a goddess on the front roof of one of the prayer halls

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: buddhist mural painting

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Life story of the buddha

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc..]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Most inscriptions depict names of the donors who sponsored specific constructions

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Red lipstick was applied on the face of several Buddha and deity statues. I have no idea how did it imply.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: often people offer buddha and deity statues to the Wat

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is it required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Monks and villagers clean and do maintenance works in the Wat particularly for the celebrations of the Khmer Tradition Year and Pchum Ben Festival every year.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Birth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Transition to adulthood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Death

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: rebirth

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: at the entrance of the temple

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Frequency of festivals

– specify: annual games which traditionally mark the end of Pchum Ben festivities

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: thousands of Cambodians

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Incubation

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Cleansing

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Expiation

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Most often people come for water blessing from monks

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 1000

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: once a year

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: For funeral, commune and general elections, communal meetings

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are they written at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are they oral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 10 CE - 21 CE